

Supplementary Material 1 (SM-1)

X-ray computed tomography measurements (CT)

Main article

Design, properties, and manufacturing of cylindrical Li-ion battery cells – A generic overview

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Figure 1. Sony / Murata US18650VTC4

Figure 2. Sony / Murata US18650VTC6

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Figure 3. Samsung INR18650-25R

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Figure 4. Samsung INR18650-35E

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Figure 5. Samsung ICR 18650-22P

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Figure 6. Sanyo UR18650RX

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Figure 7. Panasonic NCR18650B

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Figure 8. LG INR18650-MJ1

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Figure 9. LG INR18650-HG2L

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Figure 10. LG ICR 18650-HE2

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Figure 11. Sanyo Panasonic NCR2070C

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Figure 12. Panasonic NCR20700B

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Figure 13. Sony / Murata US21700VTC6A

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Figure 14. Samsung INR21700-40T

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Figure 15. Samsung INR21700-33J

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Figure 16. Samsung INR21700-50E

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Figure 17. LG Chem INR21700-M50T

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Figure 18. LG INR21700-M50LT

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